
INCLUSIVE ENTREPRENEURIAL DEVELOPMENT REFORM DIRECTION IN GEORGIA

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Abstract

It is necessary to carry out a fundamentally different state policy, which will be focused on protecting the interests of the majority of the population of the regions, i.e. small and low-income farms, recognizing their priority role in the development of the country and creating such models of development that will open up all opportunities for the free development. None of the Georgian authorities could solve this problem, directly connected with the solution of the exacerbated social problems, which largely became the reason for the low efficiency of their economic policy and, in general, the failure.

Keywords: inclusive, integration, cooperation, agro Credit Bank, paradigm, inequality, low-income, indicator.

Introduction. Today, due to the careless attitude and incorrect socio-economic policy for years, the Georgian village is highly diminished. The vast majority of the rural population is in extreme poverty and does not have the opportunity not only for entrepreneurial development, but they manage to get through everyday life with difficulty. This circumstance is largely caused by the problem of small land. Even though in recent years the government of Georgia has declared the priority of agricultural development, this approach has not been reflected in the situation of the population. In 2019, only 210 thousand hectares of land were excavated in Georgia; in 1999, 600 thousand were plowed, and in 1989 - 840 thousand. Most importantly, autumn and spring sowed areas are smaller than 10-15 years ago when the state budget practically did not fund agriculture. After a kind of revival in the agrarian sector in 2018-2020, in 2021 there is a decline again, labor productivity in this field is still low compared to other sectors of the national economy. In addition, despite the allocation of multimillion-dollar state funds in the agricultural sector, Georgia is still very weak in terms of food security, there is a permanent increase in food prices, almost 80% of food products are imported, and only in the last five years (2017-2021.) The negative balance in food exports and imports amounted to 1639.1 mln. US dollars. - This is 1.7 times higher than the average annual value-added volume created in agriculture of Georgia in the same period (962.9 million USD). In such conditions, it is practically impossible to get out of the crisis of this complex and heterogeneous system without appropriate protective mechanisms and assistance. Shortly, due to the existing and expected even deeper economic and social crisis, we are forced to respond to the challenges related to food shortages and agflation, which should become part of the strategic development plan.

Retrospective of economic policy. the economic policy of the 80-the 90s of the last century, which came

out of the depths of the atrophied bureaucratic-managerial swamp of state monopolism, practically did nothing to reduce social inequality; moreover, completely ignored it and did not even consider it as an important factor hindering the development of the country. The existing reality has already analyzed and evaluated the contradictions in modern production relations. It defined the tendency of increasing concentration of capital and land ownership and the disruptive action of the form of Labor Division as the main factor of destruction of small landowners, poverty, crises, outrageous inequality in the distribution of material wealth, breakdown of morals and family relations, and enhanced migration.

Globalization creates conditions for faster implementation of processes that have been going on for centuries in developed countries, and other relatively backward states. Small states, which connect their development with the global regularities of World dynamism, have to independently develop a policy to overcome the problems of employment and economic growth. The country is obliged to develop such economic policy, which will be directed not only to increase its competitiveness in the world market but also to solve social problems in the country. In Georgia and similar countries, problems are separated by the ratio of employment and economic growth, the solution of which is directly related to the government's efforts. The state government is the real force that influences economic regularities in the macroeconomic environment and creates specific conditions for its country's development: accelerates or hinders progress.

Under the wrong economic policy, a country may have a relatively high level of GDP in the short or medium term, but the effect of its growth will be reflected only in the bank accounts of oligarchs and politicians. The **idea of economic inclusiveness**, if we consider the high unemployment and poverty level, as well as income inequality (Gini index), has not gone beyond the format of desirability. **Economic development is a**

fundamentally different and much broader concept than economic growth. Unlike the economic growth model, the economic development model practically represents a "socially oriented economic" model and is determined not only by the level of GDP per capita but also shows the impact of economic growth directly on the economic and social conditions of the population, what is the dynamics of changes in the standard of living in the country.

Based on the overall trends of global development, it becomes necessary to observe the regularities in the world economy and develop appropriate recommendations for action. For this purpose, international organizations have proposed a "unified system of accounts", through which all countries process national statistical indicators and publish them. The ranking of countries was based on the "Human Development" index, which represents the gross domestic product per capita of the population, weighted with the average life expectancy and the level of education of the population. Indeed, it does not change the gross domestic product, which remains the main indicator of economic growth, but creates a complete idea of the inclusive development activities of the population. The issue is relevant not only for Georgia, where almost 70% of the population lives in poverty and 30% is beyond the poverty line but also for highly developed countries. The only difference is that the poor in Georgia are starving, but in the U.S., the minimum wage of the US poor is \$ 902.5 per month. It should be noted that by the number of calories consumed per person, Georgia (2835 kcal) is significantly ahead of all its land neighbors: Armenia - by 5.7%, Azerbaijan by 11.1%, Russia - by 18.0%, and Turkey by 30.9%. This situation, in connection with the high level of income, property, and consumer differentiation, makes the problem of poverty and hunger no less socio-economic (if not more) political.

In the 60s and 90s of the last century, economic policy was close to the paradigm known as the "Washington Consensus", which implies macroeconomic stabilization and the activation of private investment through the implementation of large-scale infrastructure projects, which will lead to economic growth, which in turn will eventually lead to overcoming the problem of inequality. The practice showed that poverty and inequality did not decrease in parallel with economic growth, and such a situation hindered long-term economic growth. In the 90s, the logic of the "Washington consensus", based on its results, lost its dominant function and gradually withdrew from the World Bank's economic policy, where today the paradigm of "inclusive growth" clearly dominates. Progressive economic thinking finally came to the universal recognition that the economic development of a country is a process of practical development of people, in which the decisive role is assigned to the practical activity and social relations of a person, which, in the end, is manifested in the formation of appropriate ideological foundations. According to the World Bank's assessment, economic growth is undoubtedly necessary to reduce poverty, but for growth to be sustainable, it must ensure the broad involvement of the workforce in the growth process and reduce inequality.

It has finally been proven that social inequality threatens the process of economic growth, which has led to the intensification of the paradigm of inclusive growth. Inclusive growth considers it appropriate to adopt a social policy that will promote wider involvement of factors of production in economic growth and diverge from it. The logic of "Kaldor-Hicks", according to which the main thing is economic growth and then growth redistricting through social security. Inclusive growth ensures the reduction of redistributive expenditures and the sustainability of the budget by reducing social expenditures, while the social security-oriented budget is based on poverty reduction policies through redistribution and not through productive employment, which cannot become the mainstay of inclusive growth in any way. Assessment of inclusive growth requires a complex set of indicators and the methodology developed by the World Bank (presented at the Davos Economic Forum in 2015) can be considered one of the best in this regard. The goal of inclusive growth is to promote productive employment and achieve economic growth. Briefly consider the main directions of inclusive agricultural development reform:

Agricultural sector. The low level of agricultural development has largely become the basis for poverty and high social polarization in the country, which is primarily reflected in the Gini (social inequality) index (0.40), which is the highest in post-Soviet countries after Russia. Poor populations and consequently poor countries remain poor, which is mainly because small farms (which today represent the vast majority of the rural population of Georgia) are practically impossible to save resources in the conditions of low income because all income is used for consumer purposes. The average monthly income of a household in rural Georgia in 2021 amounted to only gel 1058.7, which, taking into account current consumer prices and food rations, covers only half of the household members' Real Living Wage. According to the latest data, only soil treatment (plowing, sowing...) Already costs more than 1200 gel per hectare. Because in rural areas per household comes about 1.5 ha of land (m.Sh. Shida Kartli-1.75 ha, Kvemo Kartli-1.81 ha, Samtskhe - Javakheti - 2.21 ha, Kakheti-3.55 ha...), It turns out that only for soil cultivation the household needs about 1/6 of its annual funds. Naturally, when the current, first-line subsistence needs of the household are not fully satisfied, there can be no talk of saving funds. But if there is no saving, then there are no resources to invest. When the agrarian producer (peasant, household, farmer...) does not have the income that ensures the family's living conditions, and satisfaction of current needs, and naturally, there are no funds for investment, such a producer is actually "lost" to the market economy, remains outside the development potential of the agrarian sector.

In addition, the monetization of the economy is weak, which is another reason for the narrowing of the market. Due to poverty in Georgia, the capital is not created, which will be enough for investment activities, while the existing incomes of the population, as already mentioned above, cannot create an investment climate. As a result, poverty falls into a magical circle, and the state falls into routine captivity and lacks opportunities

to overcome the situation. **None of the Georgian authorities could solve this problem, which is directly related to the solution of the exacerbated social problems, which largely became the reason for the low efficiency of their economic policy and, in general, the failure.**

The correct choice of the form of industrial relations and the progressive socio-economic systemic changes (reforms) based on fundamentally different approaches to economic policy are of utmost importance for Georgia in the historical period, which will lead to the intensive growth of incomes of the population and the volume of national production, massive employment and will ensure the formation of an environment. In this regard, revival, and development of the village, formation of relevant infrastructure, and substantial improvement of living and activity conditions of the inhabitants of the village (equalization and/or maximum approximation) should become the driving belt. At present, in rural areas, where 40.3% of the population lives, the poverty level is 1.6-2.2 times higher than in urban areas. This does not only apply to persons engaged in agricultural activities - less than half of rural workers are directly employed in agriculture - 247.3 thousand people out of 508.2 thousand people (48.7%), the rest are employees of industrial-agricultural and social infrastructure and administrative units.

Overcoming the current situation requires a qualitatively new policy of inclusive socio-economic development.

In the current conditions, it is crucial to clearly define which organizational and legal form is closer to the social and economic mission of the state in the agrarian sector and, accordingly, which of them should be given priority in terms of state support.

International corporate experience. In the conditions of low income and low income of the absolute majority of the rural population, inclusive entrepreneurial activation, mass employment, intensive growth of production, poverty reduction, suspension of migration, and creation of long-term economic and social development prospects, the development of the Institute of cooperation is of particular importance, which, together with economic self-governance, is caused by the objective necessity of modern conditions, only large-scale production is possible to produce competitive products and accumulate a certain part of the revenues from its sale to reproduce, without which the development of the economic system and the accompanying effects cannot be achieved. The advantage of this model is in the complex nature of the main directions of support, which gives the best opportunity to approach the functioning of enterprises to the optimal. The cooperation of agricultural farms is an objective economic process. It is conditioned by the process of continuous improvement of productive forces and production relations, which requires the type of farming of organizational form corresponding to the optimal size of the land.

For effective state policy, it is of fundamental importance to categorically define: at the current stage, the difficult economic and social situation of

the rural population is a problem of particular importance, the main challenge, and the state policy should be mainly based on this issue. A democratic government should create organizational and legal conditions for the socio-economic system that will replace the ugly entrepreneurial environment. It is necessary, like the countries with developed economies, to clearly define the main point: the agricultural cooperation process is a set of large-scale activities, which for the first time in the recent history of our country is aimed directly at the benefit of the rural population and, with the final score, the whole society. We emphasize the benefit of the **rural population and not only the persons employed in agriculture** and their family members!

It is necessary to analyze in depth where the democratic principles of successful economies originate and what is its basis. It is noteworthy that these countries considered the development of the cooperative system as the priority direction for overcoming acute crises and rapid economic growth. If we look at the experience of various countries in this regard, we will see that overall the organizational structure of the economy, industrial and credit-financial relations, as well as democratic institutions, changed according to the stages of development, which was mainly related to strengthening the role of the state in establishing cooperative institutions.

The experience of agro-industrial integration and cooperation in economically developed countries provides sufficient material for their scientific and practical generalization based on systematic analysis. For example, the main reason for the success of the Spanish reforms was the development of cooperatives in agriculture, the main legal basis of which is the Constitution of Spain (1978). Article 129.2: "State bodies should effectively identify various forms of participation in production and promote the formation of cooperatives based on existing legislation". Today, up to 1 million farmers are members of Spanish agricultural cooperatives; 47% of the country's total commodity turnover and 60% of agro-food production is carried out by agricultural cooperatives. In the production of wine, fruits, vegetables, and olives, Spain ranks first in Europe.

The legal basis of the cooperative system of **Italy**, as well as **Spain**, is, first of all, Article 45 of the Constitution of the Italian Republic adopted in 1947, which states: "The Republic recognizes the social function of co-operation based on mutual assistance and not aimed at speculative purposes". In more detail, the objectives of the cooperation are set out in the Italian Civil Code, which states: "The objective of the co-operation is to create better service and working conditions for its members than the free market can provide."

In **France**, 24,000 agricultural cooperatives provide 1 million jobs and their annual total financial turnover exceeds 300 billion euros. In **Belgium**, the share of agricultural products of cooperatives in the market is quite high: milk-50%, fruits and vegetables - 70-90%, and meat - 20-30%.

Having extremely scarce natural resources, **Israel** managed to create an agricultural production system

based on a knowledge economy and innovative technologies through a cooperative system. It is through a cooperative system that the **Netherlands** has become one of the world leaders in the export of dairy products. In **Japan**, the cooperative system has shown exceptional vitality. As a result of the adoption of the law on agricultural cooperation in 1947 and the decree of the emperor of Japan, the entire population of the village was automatically included in the cooperative system, through which the government implemented a new Agrarian Policy. In the current period, 91% of Japanese farmers are members of agricultural cooperatives.

Sometimes the opinion is expressed (mainly by people who are not fully aware of the cooperative system) that the population of Georgia is not yet ready to implement large-scale cooperation projects in rural areas and they refer to a long period of development of agricultural cooperation in European countries, where it took more than 200 years to reach the existing level of development. This is an unjustified, erroneous position! Beginning in the 19th century in European countries, the process of agricultural cooperation developed stably, without any strategy, legislative-normative base, and government support. Today it is possible to give several examples of other countries, where governments, **realizing the particular impact of this process on the socio-economic strengthening of the population and economic development of the country**, made decisions on centralized large-scale support of intensive development of agricultural cooperation based on the long-term, evolutionary development experience of European countries.

Armenia, with far more scarce resources than Georgia, has managed to establish a cooperative agro-credit system that has higher self-sufficiency rates than us (especially in wheat production) and sells its agricultural products, vegetables, and even grapes on the Georgian markets.

The advantages of cooperation and its synergy effect require not only approval from the state, but also solid legal, organizational, and material support, especially towards agriculture is less adapted to market conditions (mentally, organizationally, and material-technical base) as it is in Georgia. And as a logically binding link of measures - maximum coverage of agricultural production through co-operation, bringing co-operation to a qualitatively new level.

The rules of intra-production relations of agricultural cooperation are the main component determining the identity of the agricultural cooperative as an organizational form since the introduction of these rules creates an economic environment where the determining factor of entrepreneurial activity in rural areas is not the prospect of receiving dividends from the material funds deposited in the unit fund, but a high quality of return of labor resources of the population directly involved in agricultural production. The high experience of many developed countries confirms that cooperatives ensure the reduction of social inequality, the establishment of stable production factors, and protected agroecological and innovative technologies. So, we do not need to "re-invent the wheel" in this regard.

Based on the Georgian and other experiences of coordinating the development of the cooperative sector, it is possible to clearly define the main point: the task can not be solved empirically, without taking into account theoretical and methodological aspects of the problems and preparing proper foundations, which are related to the creation of conceptual foundations of organizational, economic and financial mechanisms of development, the capitalization of labor and material resources of the population and the balancing of the economic interests of the state and the private sector.

Inclusive entrepreneurial development in rural areas. The importance of the processing industry as the main creator of added value needs in-depth understanding and a new vision because it is essential to know whose income growth is served by the added value obtained as a result of processing products and what is the result of immature policy or lack of policy about this issue. Raising the issue as if creating jobs in rural areas is the priority of economic development is self-deception and does not correspond to the real challenges facing the country and the population, because even better, job creation, in the spheres of household services, culture, health care, and other spheres and even in the processing enterprises, where 10-12 persons are employed, will not have a massive character, it will not affect on the growth of salaries of the majority of people in rural areas and on their development. This policy will be aimed at the entrepreneurial strengthening of the rich population (in most cases, people living in rural areas), and their extensive development, at the expense of discrimination of economic interests of the population producing primary agricultural products.

Inclusive entrepreneurial development of the population should become a priority of economic and social development in rural areas, which is related to the capitalization of their labor and material resources, and this should be done with the support of projects where the majority of the population will be involved and the real opportunity of which exists only for the population with a small At the current stage of historical development, the main priority of socio-economic empowerment of the rural population consists of two components:

A) support their entrepreneurial development in the agrarian sphere, not the creation of low-paid jobs with the support of a small contingent of the population;

B) development of entrepreneurial and social infrastructure in rural areas. This priority principle applies to rural residents in general and not only to those employed in agriculture.

As the gospel says, "Not only shall man live by bread" [Matthew:4; 3]. This means that the vector of development should be projected not only to agricultural workers, who fall in, as it was said above, less than half of the total contingent of rural workers but also to all rural workers and their family members, regardless of the profile of their activities.

In addition, there is a fundamental difference between rural and urban entrepreneurial industries, as the urban industry lacks those highly relevant and positive opportunities that are characteristic of rural industries, mainly processing enterprises, which can have a direct

and extremely large impact on the entrepreneurial development of hundreds and thousands of small entrepreneurs associated with these enterprises, a significant increase in their incomes and it can also create opportunities of real social and economic development.

Today, the rural population is formally free in their economic activities, but here arises the main question - to what extent can this activity be called "Entrepreneurial" and even more so "free", when, due to the lack of alternatives, the population is forced to hand over its products to an LLC-type processing enterprise, which dictates discriminatory prices and conditions for delivery. - The difference between the delivery price of primary raw materials and the price of finished products obtained by processing them is generally high (sometimes 10-15 times and even more), i.e. due to the existing pricing mechanism and "price scissors", the share of primary raw materials in the final retail prices and, accordingly, the share of peasants (farmers) producing them is more than 2-4 times less. Over the past 30 years, the primary agricultural products produced by the rural population have been procured in most cases at prices set by cartel agreements between LLC-type processing plants and intermediary organizations, which in many cases cannot compensate for the costs incurred for the production of these products. It is clear that such an approach contradicts the interests of the rural population and brings only a backlash for them, because the economic process is directed not at agro-producers, but at satisfying the interests of LLC-type processing enterprise owners and intermediaries, at the expense of discrimination of agro-producers' interests. A discriminative price ceiling for the purchase of products is set for the population, which is practically impossible to change because this change far exceeds the limited capacity of low-income populations. Accordingly, they officially have the right to the free sale of products, but this right is practically restricted due to monopolies and cartel agreements established at the later economic stage of production. It is particularly noteworthy that such entrepreneurial relations are too narrow to occupy the labor, material, and intellectual potential of the entire population.

Based on the analysis of the modern state of agrarian development of the country, it is theoretically substantiated that the processing industry, as the most important link in the creation of value-added in a single production cycle, acquires special importance in the framework of agricultural cooperation, since it is in this system that it can acquire the function of serving the population. Vertically integrated cooperative enterprises producers of primary agricultural products will organize a unified production cycle of processing, packaging, storage, and sale of their products and generate added value, where the added value increases at each economic stage, and they will receive significantly increased income from the sale of final products. The place will have a double positive effect:

A. The synergy cooperation itself ensures the large-scale increase of its members' incomes by reducing non-production and duplicated costs;

B. The cooperation significantly reduces the price discrimination that individual producers currently face when dealing with LLC-type processing enterprises.

Accordingly, we will get the most important socio-economic results: mass employment of the rural population (currently, the unemployment rate in the villages is quite high - 18.2%), large-scale production, qualified management, reduction of cost, successful operation of marketable segments, minimization of entrepreneurial risks, intensive and balanced development of agricultural sectors.

In terms of inclusive entrepreneurial development of the population, the cooperative sector is much more capable, because one or several persons are engaged in entrepreneurial activities in an LLC when hundreds of people can get high returns under the conditions of investment in the cooperative in the same volume. **This position should not be understood as if the purely economic aspect of the development of the economic system is somehow restricted by raising a social issue in the economic process. On the contrary, it is precisely the priority of a well-thought-out, correct economic mechanism that allows the optimal synthesis of two basic principles of distribution of material economic and ethical.**

Community cooperatives. In determining the optimal form of local territorial distribution of agricultural cooperation, priority importance is given to community cooperatives. Their formation will take place within the framework of administrative units, taking into account the factors of specialization of production and concentration of production forces. Community "Gemeinschaft" (German)- This is the most natural and sustainable form of collective unity. In Georgia, especially in the mountainous regions, it has historically been a union of blood relatives and families living in their neighborhood, where people are connected by geographic, religious, cultural, psychological, economic, and defense interests and are directed to permanent strengthening. Community cooperatives ensure mass involvement of the population in the cooperative process, where it is possible to use the scale effect and capitalize on the opportunities and material resources of the population to multiply the productive forces as quickly as possible and create a solid foundation for inclusive entrepreneurial development.

Cooperation does not deprive anyone of property. It only deprives itself of the opportunity to devalue the labor of others by appropriating the product of joint labor. Community cooperatives are most capable of creating the basis for the successful implementation of common agricultural activities, which will bring the most important problems related to the separation of lands within the framework of strict social coordination.

The land is the main production base for Inclusive Development. It should be noted that as a result of immature activities in the agrarian sphere, an objective circumstance is created that LLC-type processing enterprises and intermediary organizations supported by state programs become oriented to extensive development, which is manifested in the expansion of their

lands at the expense of purchasing land from the population. They benefit from the fact that peasants who are invulnerable to individual entrepreneurial activities, who are confronted with many internal or external problems of various nature, who are separated and deprived of necessary support, are forced to sell their lands due to extreme hardship, which is accompanied by irreparable consequences for them and which has recently become massive.

Land for a farmer/peasant is not only a means of production but also an organic part of determining his/her essence as a socio-economic and national subject. Therefore, the issue of land purchase and sale, along with socioeconomic, has great national importance. Cutting off a peasant from the land will result in the destruction of his / her function as an entrepreneurial entity and, better, turn him/her into an object of hired labor. A hired person makes up a simple supplement to the process of accumulating someone else's capital, who is required to perform only simple, easily digestible, and monotonous work. His rental costs are determined only by the subsistence minimum he needs to save himself. Even today, due to the shortage of this type of work, low-income residents are forced to agree to discriminatory conditions for work.

The attitude towards land and correct Land Management Policy, due to its particular importance for the country and the population, should fulfill an important, one might say, determining function in the structuring of the Georgian state. It can be said that in the conditions of segregated lands in Georgia, the development of the mechanism of land redemption from the population can be justified only for consolidation of the Lands, development of the land market, and their maintenance. Especially, when most of the agricultural lands in Georgia are unprotected and untreated and the able-bodied, healthy population massively travels abroad to work on other lands. It is extremely important and alarming that in such conditions, the institution of the family is naturally destroyed, and the relations valuable for a person are degraded and then disappear. Historically established sensitive phrases about the family, the gentle relationship between parents and children, and upbringing are transformed into mere words.

The need to form a specialized agro-credit system. In the current conditions, without support, the existence of small farms in rural areas is possible only at a low technological level, which cannot ensure their development in any way. With state support and regulation, those functions are performed that are not provided by self-regulating market levers. State financing and regulation of agricultural cooperative systems are distinguished by complex structures and complex approaches defined normatively. The placement of budgetary funds in the agrarian sector on preferential terms and their control by the state is carried out within the framework of state-targeted programs. The development and realization of these programs are carried out by the state based on complex approaches, which means that the project should cover the entire system of agricultural production in a particular direction.

To provide the rural population with credit resources, the formation of a cooperative agro-credit system is of particular importance. In developed economies, the main component of the cooperative agro-credit system is mainly represented as the **cooperative agro-credit Bank (CACB)**, although in some countries this system is created by **credit unions** and/or credit divisions of agricultural cooperatives. The cooperative Credit Bank is a targeted policy mechanism in the agrarian sector, the purpose of which is to increase the efficiency of labor and material resources of its members, which is achieved through preferential and simplified terms of lending, low-interest rates, joint responsibility, mutual trust and elimination of corruption manifestations, where the cooperative model of entrepreneurial activity and cooperative intra-production relations are a factor of lower risk when it comes to giving credits. Shareholders are well aware of each other's activities and, based on the principle of joint responsibility, exert pressure on so-called bad borrowers. If the debt cannot be repaid by any shareholder, other members of the cooperative cannot receive additional credit.

Conclusion. It is necessary to carry out a fundamentally different state policy, which will be focused on protecting the interests of the absolute majority of the population of the regions, i.e. small-scale and low-income farms, recognizing their priority role in the development of the country and creating such models of development that will open all opportunities for all the possibilities of free development.

The introduction of adequate and effective elements of the challenges in the system of state support and regulation will contribute to the effective institutional arrangement and will create a solid basis for overcoming the obstacles that hinder the transformation of the agrarian sector into an expanded system of diverse financial relations. Insufficient awareness of the fact that the development of rural cooperation in the current conditions is the most important direction of state reforms and transformations, and refraining from taking adequate effective measures in this regard and sharing the rich experience of successful economies, creates insurmountable problems that make economic and social development of rural population impossible.

The creation of a cooperative agro-credit system is necessary for providing credit for the entrepreneurial activities of the rural population. The development of the agricultural cooperation process is mainly determined by the coordinating body (agency) and the cooperative agro credit bank because, in the current conditions, only their organic tandem determines the expediency and successful functioning of each of them. Consequently, their existence separately lacks an objective basis.

In the current conditions, to choose the right path of economic development of the country, it is necessary to clearly and categorically define: when there are strong economic motives and especially models for the development of inclusive agro-enterprise activities that affect the improvement of socio-economic conditions of numerous members of the society, their ignorance or consideration in the rank of parity.

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